

THE USE OF THERMAL ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES FOR THE STUDY OF THE CURING OF PRE-PREG RESINS AND COMPOSITE CHARACTERISATION

J. K. Arthur*, P. A. Larcey*, G. M. Savage⁺ and P. Cox⁺

* Polymer Laboratories (Epsom) Ltd, Surrey Business Park, Epsom, Surrey, KT17 1JF, England

+ McLaren International Ltd, Woking, England

ABSTRACT

Thermal analytical techniques, such as differential scanning calorimetry, thermogravimetry and dynamic mechanical spectroscopy, are being widely used in the determination of pre-preg properties and the characterisation of final composite bodies. By using these techniques it is possible to measure glass transition temperature and lower temperature transitions, Cure reaction/kinetics, fibre properties and weight loss.

Several examples of pre-preg and composites will illustrate the powerful nature of thermal analysis. These techniques will help the composite design engineer achieve superior performance from the materials available today and also guide the material scientist to the materials of the future.

Keywords: Fibre reinforced composites, Epoxy resins, Carbon-carbon composites, Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis, Differential Thermal Analysis, Thermogravimetric Analysis, Simultaneous Thermal Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The role of fibre reinforced materials has grown rapidly over the past decade and there seems every indication that this will continue. This rapid growth has mainly been at the expense of the more traditional engineering metallic alloys. The main advantage in these materials is not on the basis of strength and stiffness alone, but mostly on the relation between the modulus per unit weight (specific modulus) and strength per unit weight (specific strength). The higher specific modulus and specific strength of component materials means that the overall weight of components can be reduced. This is an important factor as reductions in weight result in greater efficiency and energy savings. To make the maximum use of these materials it is necessary to understand the difficult design parameters that effect the selection of both fibres and matrix systems, the effect of changes in frequency, stress/strain and most importantly, temperature.

In order to characterise these parameters a family of analytical techniques generally referred to as Thermal Analysers (TA) can be used. This encompasses simple thermogravimetry

(TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and the more complex dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA).

In this paper we give several examples of thermal analysis applied to composite studies and show how this family of techniques can be used to provide information to the composite design engineer that can in turn help to increase performance of current materials, and focus on future developments.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES AND THEORY

All the data presented in this paper was obtained by using the Thermal Analysis instrumentation of Polymer Laboratories Ltd. A brief description of these techniques and the appropriate theory is listed below. For more in depth explanation and theoretical background the following excellent reviews are suggested [1-5].

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) is the most simple of all the various thermoanalytical techniques. It consists of measuring the weight change of a known mass of material as a function of temperature (or time) in a controlled atmosphere. This allows studies of many typical composite applications such as degradation effects of temperature ramps and atmospheres, and oxidation rate determinations.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry One of the earliest thermal analysis techniques was Differential Thermal Analysis (DTA). This should not be confused with the DSC method. DTA is a technique in which the difference in temperature between sample and a reference material is monitored against time or temperature while the temperature of the sample, in a specified atmosphere, is programmed. DSC is a technique in which the heat flow rate (power) to the sample is monitored against time or temperature while the temperature of the sample, in a specified atmosphere, is programmed. In practice, the difference in heat flow rate to a pan containing the sample and to a reference pan (empty or not) is monitored.

It is important to understand the fundamental difference between a DTA and a DSC. From the two definitions given by ICTA [6] this is clearly that a DTA simply measures T whereas DSC monitors the flow of energy into or from a sample material. From the data obtained by DSC it is possible to study the following areas of composite characterisation: Heat capacity vs temperature or time allows measurement of heats of fusion; Identification of crystalline phases, the degree of crystallinity; Glass transition (T_g) measurement allows characterisation of ageing, blend compatibilities; Heats of reaction allow cure and degradation studies.

Simultaneous Thermal Analysis (STA) This technique combines both TGA and DSC in one instrument, thus enabling more direct studies between weight loss and energy reactions.

Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis (DMTA) The DMTA technique differs from DSC in that it measures molecular motion in polymers, and not heat change. The technique relies on impressing a small sinusoidally varying stress on to the material under test and transducing the strain. The time-dependent response is shown in Figure 1a. For a completely elastic material the strain is in phase with the stress, and for a purely viscous material the strain lags behind the stress by 90° (out of phase). Polymers are viscoelastic to a greater or lesser extent according to the temperature at which they are measured. It is thus convenient to resolve this behaviour into an in-phase elastic-like component (governed by the storage modulus E' or G') and an out-of-phase viscous-like component (governed by the loss

modulus E" or G"). The lower curves in Fig. 1 show the stress response broken down into the in-phase and out-of-phase components with respect to the strain response.

The storage and loss moduli are now defined by:

$$\text{Storage Modulus} = \frac{\text{inphase stress amplitude}}{\text{strain amplitude}} = C/B$$

$$\text{Loss Modulus} = \frac{\text{Out-of-phase stress amplitude}}{\text{strain amplitude}} = D/B$$

These relationships can be summarised in an Argand diagram with the total response governed by the complex modulus (E^*, G^*) as shown in Fig. 1b. The phase angle (lag of strain behind stress) is also clearly defined in the Argand diagram and a convenient dimensionless parameter is the loss tangent ($\tan \delta$):

$$\begin{aligned} \tan \delta &= G''/G' \text{ (in shear)} \\ \text{or } \tan \delta &= E''/E' \text{ (for Youngs Modulus)} \end{aligned}$$

This is physically the ratio of energy lost to energy stored per deformation cycle. A peak in $\tan \delta$ occurs when the impressed frequency matches the frequency of molecular relaxation through thermally activated processes.

The Polymer Laboratories' DMTA is shown in schematic view (Fig. 2). This instrument uses direct-phase measurement between the stress and strain sine waves in a frequency range of 0.01 Hz to a few hundred Hz. Thermal Scanning or stepped isothermal are the normal method of acquiring DMTA data and it is thus desirable, by frequency multiplexing or by simultaneous frequency applications, to acquire data at several frequencies during the scan. It has a dynamic stiffness range of four decades which covers all typical relaxations found in composite materials.

Suitable clamp configurations have also been designed to take account of the high moduli found in some composites (moduli as high as 10^{11} Pa in the fibre directions). Due to the large size of the clamping bars and the furnace it is possible to use a comparatively long sample which overcomes the inherent stiffness of composites and therefore avoids massive end-correction errors.

Experimental Results

1. Fibre property determination. DMTA thermal scans run in the tensile mode show that both kevlar and carbon high strength fibre is constant over a working temperature range up to and above 500°C (Fig. 3a + b).
2. Pre-preg processing: By using a PL-STA 625 it is possible to determine the cure reaction peak for an epoxy (see Fig. 4a) resin matrix. Using this method we can maximise the extent of cure by applying the Borchardt & Daniels (B + D) kinetic model. (This model assumes that the cure reaction curve is Gaussian). Once the kinetic model is applied it is possible to generate an isothermal conversion/time plot. This yields information on the percent conversion (cure) of the pre-preg against time

(Fig. 4b). Small sample sizes and rapid analysis of prepreg cure using the PL-STA 625 means materials can be fully characterised at little expense, thus giving a direct advantage over competitors.

3. The PL-DMTA can be used to examine the properties of material in service. Thermal scans (Fig. 5a + b) show two epoxy composite cured at different temperatures (120°C and 180°C) with high and intermediate modulus carbon fibres. The scans reveal that the composites retain constant modulus until they approach their glass transition (T_g 's) temperatures of the epoxy matrix. At this point the modulus of most composites fall by an order of magnitude[7]. An interesting point is seen on the $\tan \delta$ trace that smaller molecular relaxations occur at temperatures lower than the T_g . This may be due to fibre/matrix interface, or transitions within the epoxy. These are commonly known as β and γ transitions.

The important effect of cure on final engineering properties of the composite can therefore be determined at the pre-preg stage if sufficient analysis is carried out using suitable kinetic models to obtain the maximum (i.e. 100%) cure reaction of the matrix.

4. Effects of atmosphere on the degradation studies of composite in use is easily determined using either TGA or STA techniques. Fig. 6a shows an epoxy/carbon fibre composite having been ramped up to 1000°C in air. We can observe the effect of rapid oxidation causing massive weight loss of the material.

Running the same material at the same ramp and final temperature (1000°C) in nitrogen shows the stability of composite material in an inert atmospheres even when subjected to extreme service conditions. By using a series of isothermal conditions and differing ramp temperatures it is possible to obtain oxidative kinetic data from these techniques. Both these instruments can be linked to evolved gas analysis (Mass Spec, FTIR) and can be used to study the chemical degradation of composite material.

CONCLUSION

The various thermal analysis techniques are an invaluable tool in the production and research of fibre reinforced composite materials. A complete characterisation of the cure parameters of thermoset based materials can be carried out both for QC purposes and to optimise production. Composite fabrication differs from metals production in that the component manufacturer is required to carry out a complex chemical reaction, the cure, in order to make the product. The performance of a composite structure will depend very much on how the cure reaction is carried out since the design criterial will assume a perfect stress transfer between fibres and matrix. Thermal analysis can be used to check the quality of raw materials, evaluate gel times, optimise cure cycles and check components are fully cured. As a research tool equipment such as STA and DMTA may be used to simulate actual operating environments to ensure that the material is capable of undertaking a particular application. Typical examples of this are oxidation studies on carbon-carbon composites, T_g evaluation and Isothermal DMTA studies on composite mechanical response over long time periods at elevated temperatures.

The major advantage of thermal analysis is that a wealth of important information may be obtained very quickly from very small samples. Computer control and data analysis allows a complete thermochemical evaluation of composite materials and a qualitative assessment of their performance under simulated operation conditions. The requirement for only small sample sizes is particularly useful since many of the materials to be tested are extremely expensive.

REFERENCES

1. Analysis of Thermally Stimulated Processes
R. Chen and Y. Kirsh
Pergamon Press, 1981
2. Anelastic and Dielectric Effects in Polymeric Solids
D. G. McCrum, B. E. Read and G. Williams
Dover Publications, 1992
3. Polymer Characterisation, Chapter 7 (Thermal Analysis)
R. E. Wetton (Ed. B. J. Hunt and M. I. James)
Blackie Academic + Professional, 1993
4. Determination of Elastic and Mechanical Properties, Vol. VII, Chapter 1
(Determination of Dynamic Moduli and Loss Factors)
B. E. Read, G. D. Dean and J. C. Duncan
John Wiley, 1991
5. Carbon - Carbon Composites
Dr G Savage
Chapman and Hall, 1993
6. For Better Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry, Edition III
Ed. J O Hill
International Confederation for Thermal Analysis (ICTA), 1991
7. An Introduction to Composite Materials
D. Hull
Cambridge University Press, 1988

Fig. 1a Sinusoidal varying stress and strain in a dynamic mechanical experiment. Construction shows definition of $E' = C/B$ and $E'' = D/B$.

Fig. 1b Argand diagram showing relationship between complex modulus E^* (G^* for shear), Storage modulus E' (G'), loss modulus E'' (G'') and $\tan \delta$

Fig. 2 Schematic view of PL-DMTA Mk III

DMTA

Head: Combined 500°C
Polymer Laboratories

KEYLAR FIBRE
FREQUENCY : 1 Hz
STRAIN : X1
DIM: 9.78, 0.610, 0.021

Fig 3a : DMTA Scan Kevlar fibre

VERSION: V5.30

STA 625

Polymer Laboratories

PrePreg
Gas : Static Air
Size : 12.100 mg

Fig 4a : PL-STAG25 scan of pre-preg cure reactions with (B+D) kinetic model analysis applied

VERSION: V5.30

DMTA

Head: Combined 500°C
Polymer Laboratories

CARBON FIBRE (HS)
FREQUENCY : 1 Hz
STRAIN : X1
DIM: 9.48, 0.552, 0.031

Fig 3b : DMTA Scan Carbon HS fibre

VERSION: V5.30

STA 625

Polymer Laboratories

PrePreg
Gas : Static Air
Size : 12.100 mg

Fig 4b : Isothermal conversion of above curve, showing percent conversion (cure) v's time for a series of 10°C steps

VERSION: V5.30

DMTA

Head: Combined 500°C
Polymer Laboratories

120°C FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY
FREQUENCY : 1Hz
STRAIN : X1
3Pt BENDING MODE

Fig 5a : DMTA thermal scan. 120°C cure on epoxy/intermediate strength carbon fibre.

VERSION: VS.33

TGA 1500

Polymer Laboratories

180°C FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY
Gas : AIR at 40%
Size : 10.970 mg
Heating Rate : 10°C/min

Fig 5a : TGA trace of Epoxy composite in air

VERSION: VS.30

DMTA

Head: Combined 500°C
Polymer Laboratories

180°C FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY
FREQUENCY : 1 Hz
STRAIN : X1
3Pt BENDING MODE

Fig 5b : DMTA thermal scan. 180°C cure on epoxy/high strength carbon fibre.

VERSION: VS.33

TGA 1500

Polymer Laboratories

180°C FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY
Gas : N2 at 40%
Size : 8.380 mg
Heating Rate : 10°C/min

Fig 5b : TGA trace of Epoxy composite in nitrogen

VERSION: VS.30